

The Understanding of “Development” in the Documents of the Magisterium

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Abstract: The deepening of the understanding of ‘development’ in the Church as well as outside has been slow. Initially, the emphasis was more on economic development. Gradually the emphasis shifted to integral development or social development. Through social analysis we came to know that poverty in the world is purposely maintained by the vested interests of a few wealthy individuals or nations. Hence, economic development alone will not be able to address this issue of poverty and underdevelopment. There are various forces working against the integral development of individuals and nations. Faulty religious beliefs and practices, wastage of money in prestigious programmes, exaggerated defence expenses, structural adjustment policies, new economic policies, globalisation, invasion of multinational companies, voluntary retirement scheme, utter selfishness, large scale corruption, unequal treatment of women, high illiteracy rate, lack of health facilities for the poor, unemployment, underemployment, child labour, etc., are some of the factors which hinder the growth process. India as a nation is moving towards becoming a developed nation, but wealth is concentrated in the hands of the top ten percent of the people. As a result the gap between the rich and the poor is steadily increasing. The Church in India has been successful to a great extent in its attempts at education and health care. Since there are many landlords and politicians who are opposed to education and development, the Church personnel are facing strong opposition by way of persecution, false legal cases, intimidation, etc.

Keywords: The Church, Vatican II, poverty, education and development, *Gaudium et Spes*, *Populorum Progressio*, *Evangelii Nuntiandi*, *Sollicitudo Rei Socialis*.

Introduction

The question of development is a complex issue: who decides what development means and for whom. The idea of 'development' has undergone change and development over the years. The first part of this article deals with the attempts at development in India. This will give us the context in which the growth in the understanding of development in four major Church's magisterial documents of the past fifty years is discussed.

Initially, the term 'development' was used mainly to denote economic development. Thus, many social activists tried to bring about development by introducing modern methods of agriculture and other economic activities to improve the standard of living of the rural poor. According to them, lack of capital was the cause of underdevelopment. "The solution, therefore, was to promote economic growth by an infusion of capital, which would lead to industrialization and eventual prosperity."¹

But those third world countries which adopted this model ended up with 'economic stagnation coupled with political and social unrest'.² The main reason for this was the unjust trade relations between the developed and the underdeveloped nations.

Many of these projects were funded by the government and some foreign funding agencies. But since these activities failed to achieve the desired aim, the need was felt to give importance to the fields of health and education. Again, the rapid rate of population growth hindered any attempt at development. So family planning programmes were also introduced as part of the process of development.³

Now we are slowly moving away from and beyond purely economic development to social development. "The concept of social development is inclusive of economic development but differs from it in the sense that it emphasises the development of the totality of society in its economic, political, social, and cultural aspects."⁴ Social development basically means an integrated development of the whole person. This concept does not accept that economic development is the basis of other forms of development. It stresses the simultaneous development of the different areas.

Development in India

A country like India is on the road to becoming a developed nation and its GNP is going up rather rapidly. At the same time a large number of people in our country continue to remain below the poverty line. Due to the effects of globalisation and other similar trends many have lost their jobs and remain unemployed or underemployed. Hence, a small percentage of people are becoming very rich at the expense of the development of the majority.

India is said to be a rich country with poor people residing in it. India has very rich resources, but somehow these resources are not well utilized. The 'mixed economy' policy did not bear the desired result. "Coupled with these economic problems were the mismanagement of funds, consecutive elections, corruption of high magnitude at all levels, inefficiency, clamour for higher wages not backed by productive increase, high military expenditures, and expenses on populist programmes."⁵ Due to large scale corruption the facilities meant for the poorer sections often ended up in the hands of the well-off people. When India requested the IMF help to recover from the economic crisis, we had to accept their conditions of economic liberalization and Structural Adjustment Policies (SAP). These policies include 'encouraging greater participation of the private sector, disinvestments in state owned public sector enterprises, deregulation of industries, liberalisation of foreign trade and foreign investment and changes in fiscal policy'.⁶

The consequences of liberalisation are very damaging to the general public. A large number of people have lost their jobs under the names of 'Golden Handshake' and the 'Voluntary Retirement Scheme'. "Between 1991-94 it is estimated that about 75,000 in the public sector and 1,25,000 in the private sector have been sent out."⁷ When more and more people are losing their jobs, even if the industries make profits, this cannot be seen as integral development. In order to keep them economically viable, Industries have to go in for modern technologies with less employees. The agriculture sector will not be able to employ many more people if it has to run profitably. "Therefore, the unorganised sector, with its large scope for self-employment, must expand rapidly in order to create the additional jobs."⁸

One sign of economic development is the movement of the labour force from the unorganised to the organised sector, where they form their own unions and their interests are taken care of. But in India, due to the New Economic Policies, the reverse process is taking place creating more and more casual labourers. Among the casual labourers, the number of women and children are on the increase. “Multinational companies are keen in exploiting such cheap labour by sub-contracting the various production processes.”⁹ The developed countries are making use of India for their continued wealth accumulation.

The Church and Development

Till the middle of the 20th century, the Church was involved in preaching the gospel to those who had never heard of Jesus and in the work of charity, education and health care. To be concerned about developmental activities was not considered part of its mission. Today the Church accepts developmental activities and promotion of justice as part and parcel of its evangelising mission. The synodal document, ‘Justice in the World’, considers “action on behalf of justice and participation in the transformation of the world as a constitutive dimension of the preaching of the Gospel”.¹⁰ In the recent past the Church has been very active in Northeast India with a view to evangelisation. Along with evangelisation, the Church was very active in the apostolate of human development.¹¹

Though many Church documents deal with the topic of development, I like to restrict myself to the study of only four documents: Vatican II’s Pastoral Constitution on The Church in the Modern World (*Gaudium et Spes*), the encyclical of Pope Paul VI on The Development of Peoples (*Populorum Progressio*) and his Apostolic Exhortation on Evangelisation in the Modern World (*Evangelii Nuntiandi*) and the encyclical of John Paul II on Social Concern (*Sollicitudo Rei Socialis*).

Magisterial Teaching on Development

Gaudium et Spes

Gaudium et Spes of Vatican II (1965) seems to give the impression that ‘development’ would be able to solve the problems of poverty.

Many of the bishops and experts at the Council might have believed that the best way to promote international social justice and overcome poverty was to opt for a Western-style development. The assumption behind this approach is that Western-style 'development' can be imitated. Developing nations could follow the same path of development as the developed nations during the last two centuries.¹² Yet this may only lead to the creation of a Fourth or even a Fifth World.

The responsibility for development of the underdeveloped nations is laid both on the developing as well as on the developed nations. Developing nations need to be concerned about the complete human fulfilment of all their citizens as the explicit goal of progress. "Let them be mindful that progress begins and develops primarily from the efforts and endowments of the people themselves. Hence, instead of depending solely on outside help, they should rely chiefly on the full unfolding of their own resources and the cultivation of their own qualities and tradition."¹³

The document also points to the responsibility of the developed nations. "The development of any nation depends on human and financial assistance... The developing nations will be unable to procure the necessary material assistance unless the practices of the modern business world undergo a profound change. Additional help should be offered by advanced nations, in the form of either grants or investments."¹⁴

Gaudium et Spes recognizes that a major source of injustice in international trade is the inequality in power between trading partners. In order to regulate this inequality, the document calls for the setting up of effective institutions to promote a just economic order.¹⁵ "Let adequate organizations be established for fostering and harmonizing international trade, especially with respect to the less advanced countries, and for repairing the deficiencies caused by an excessive disproportion in the power possessed by various nations."¹⁶

GS is not content with a conversion in the mentality and attitudes of peoples, but also calls for reforms in the socio-economic realm. "Numerous reforms are needed at the socio-economic level, along with universal change in ideas and attitudes."¹⁷ The Council says

that in many situations there is urgent need for a reassessment of economic and social structures.¹⁸ The term 'reassessment' suggests that the Council does not identify itself with those who fight for the overthrowing of the existing structures. But what is significant is that the Council Fathers did not shy away from calling for a reassessment. They did not start with the assumption that any fundamental restructuring is unnecessary, nor did they rule it out on the ground that it might lead to some confusion in society.¹⁹

GS also cautions against sudden technical solutions at the cost of the priceless heritage of the non-Western cultures. "But nations must beware of technical solutions immaturely proposed, especially those which offer man material advantage while militating against his spiritual nature and development. For, 'Not by bread alone does man live, but by every word that comes forth from the mouth of God' (Mt 4:4). Each branch of the human family possesses in itself and in its worthier traditions some part of the spiritual treasure entrusted by God to humanity, even though many do not know the source of this treasure."²⁰

GS speaks of deep compassion for the poor, but gives no clear indication of solidarity with them. It seems to be more concerned about doing something for the poor rather than being with the poor. GS presents poverty as an urgent problem which is to be overcome mainly by 'development'.

Populorum Progressio

Populorum Progressio was issued on 26th March 1967 by Pope Paul VI barely sixteen months after the Council Document, *Gaudium et Spes*. This shows his great commitment to the problem of development. This encyclical deals with the relationship between rich and poor nations. Pope Paul VI is concerned about the problem of poverty and he wants to find out its basic causes before he suggests any solution. He points out that the main causes of poverty are the negative effects of colonialism in the past, neo-colonialism and the huge difference of wealth and power between nations.²¹ Though he speaks of the negative effects of colonialism as one of the reasons for poverty, he mentions that colonialism has also done some good to the people by way of diminishing ignorance and sickness. He is of the

opinion that colonialism has also brought better communications and improved the living conditions of the people. ²²

The Pope is of the opinion that the social problems cannot be solved at the national level alone. PP deals with the challenge of integral development. He condemns unbridled liberalism. “However certain concepts have somehow arisen out of these new conditions and insinuated themselves into the fabric of human society. These concepts present profit as the chief spur to economic progress, free competition as the guiding norm of economics, and the private ownership of means of production as an absolute right, having no limits, nor concomitant social obligations.”²³

He emphasizes the role of the Church in the process of development and gives a Christian vision of development. The Pope envisages a well integrated development of everyone. “What must be aimed at is complete humanism. And what is that if not the fully rounded development of the whole man and of all men?”²⁴ The development of a nation is to be judged by the level of development of the last and the least. This calls for a commitment to justice and equality for all the citizens. “This commitment is to the historical project of the poor, whereby the non-persons become persons and agents or subjects of their own history and cease to be objects of exploitation and manipulated history.”²⁵ The development of every person is mediated by the option for the development of the last and the least.

Jesus is our model for commitment to the development of the poor and the marginalized. Jesus came to proclaim the good news of the Kingdom of God to the poor. He had a preferential love for the poor and this was shown by his close association with them. His personal life and ministry were directed towards the liberation of the oppressed and the downtrodden. He reinterpreted the Sabbath for the benefit of the poor and the heavy burdened. Jesus’ commitment to everyone was mediated through his preferential option for the poor.

He suggests economic planning and aid to promote development²⁶. He concludes by terming ‘development’ the new name for peace, and exhorts all Christians to strive for true development. “For if the new name for peace is development, who would not wish to labour for it

with all his powers?"²⁷ He feels that revolution is not the right means to bring about human development, but he points out that if the interests of the poor people are not given proper importance, they may be forced to have recourse to violence.²⁸ At the same time he also mentions that a revolutionary uprising will only produce new injustices, imbalances, and disasters.²⁹ The Pope is quite optimistic when he says that despite all its failures, the world is in fact moving towards greater brotherhood and an increase in humanity.³⁰

We cannot expect integral development to take place from the top. "We have a tendency to consider the poor as the problem: the fact is that they are emerging as the solution!"³¹ Many groups are slowly emerging all over the world which challenge the oppressive forces. We need to look up to these groups and support them so that they may bring about meaningful changes in the society.

Evangelii Nuntiandi

In *Evangelii Nuntiandi* (1975), Pope Paul VI deals with the controversial theological question raised by the document of the Synod on 'Justice in the World', when it said that action on behalf of justice is a constitutive dimension of preaching the Gospel.³² According to EN, the Church is a community of believers gathered 'in the name of Jesus so that they may together seek the Kingdom, build it up and implement in their own lives'.³³ Building the Kingdom is not confined to the so called 'religious' or 'spiritual' activities. It also requires secular activities such as working for the integral development of people and struggling against the oppressive and inhuman structures in the society.

In *Gaudium et Spes* and *Populorum Progressio* the main emphasis is on development rather than liberation. Starting from the Medellin documents there is a shift from development to liberation. Pope Paul in writing *Octogesima Adveniens* in 1971 was very cautious in his use of the word 'liberation'. In EN he provides a thorough theological analysis of the concept of liberation. He writes that the main purpose of the coming of Jesus was to proclaim the Good News of the Kingdom of God. He summarises the content of the Good News: "As the main point and the very centre of his Good News, Christ proclaims salvation; this is the great gift of God which is liberation from everything that oppresses people, particularly liberation from sin and the Evil One..."³⁴ It is not

possible to preach the Good News without questioning the dehumanising structures of society. The Good News about the risen Lord is the news of liberation from poverty, oppression and injustice. Even though the word liberation goes beyond economic and political liberation, it cannot replace the word 'salvation'. Salvation is a gift of God. It begins in this life but is fulfilled only in eternity.

The Pope gives an overall vision of evangelisation, one that transcends any division such as 'religious versus secular' or 'spiritual versus temporal'. All the same the mission of the Church should not be reduced to merely a temporal project.³⁵ If that were not the case, the Church would have nothing more to offer than the social activists or political movements. EN understands evangelisation as bringing "the Good News into all the strata of the human race so that by its power it may permeate the depths of humanity and make it new".³⁶ There is a need for inner transformation. External transformation brought about by force will not be lasting unless it is supported by love and concern for fellow human beings. It means "affecting the standards by which people make judgments, their prevailing values, their interests and thought-patterns, the things that move them to action, and their models of human living".³⁷

Preaching of the Good News is to be done by all Christians. This task involves working for an integral development and liberation of all peoples. Every Christian has to use his special God-given talent and charism for the betterment of the whole society. Every one is called to contribute his/her might for the building up of the Kingdom of God, which Jesus came to establish.³⁸

Sollicitudo Rei Socialis

Dated December 31, 1987, published in February 1988, the encyclical *Sollicitudo Rei Socialis* by Pope John Paul II commemorates the 20th anniversary of *Populorum Progressio*. Its purpose was to re-examine attempts made in the field of development during the intervening twenty years. The Pope comes to the conclusion that the efforts at development failed in many areas. The Pope says that education and easy access to information are among the most positive means of achieving development. He also feels that there is a need for radical political reforms in order to achieve them. He finds the conflict between East and West

of over forty years has been a cause for the Third World to remain underdeveloped. The resources that could have been used for the development of the Third World countries were used for the accumulation of weapons.³⁹

The Encyclical points out that integrated development can take place only in a culture which promotes initiative. Of course the Pope has in mind the situation of the Eastern block, which was suppressing personal initiatives. Democratic forms of government seem to be the best for true development of all people. The people become the subjects rather than the objects of development.⁴⁰ In order to get participation of the general public, they have to be somehow made participants in decision making and implementation. The Indian government's attempt at *panchayati raj* is a good starting point. At the same time it is very difficult to get the support of all the people due to various reasons. "In India, the existence of religious minorities and the claims of regional linguistic loyalties have created difficulties at the national level and the differentiation based on caste has vitiated local regional politics."⁴¹ Because of the very low percentage of literacy, the illiterate masses tend to believe in the false promises made by politicians for their own political advantage.

The Pope gives a broad meaning to development and he says that the poor as well as the rich need development. Along with economic and social development there is a need for moral development. This means that the attitudes of people have to be changed along with the external manifestations of development. It is a pity that underdevelopment goes hand in hand with superdevelopment. Those who enjoy superdevelopment become slaves of their possessions and they cultivate a culture of consumerism and 'throw-away'⁴². Pope John Paul II uses the term 'solidarity' in order to explain the duty of the developed nations to come to the aid of the developing nations and to treat them as their 'neighbours' and 'helpers'.⁴³ The Pope insists that one's neighbour is 'the living image of God the Father, redeemed by the blood of Jesus Christ and placed under the permanent action of the Holy Spirit'.⁴⁴ Solidarity also implies that the material goods as well as the products of human industry should belong to everyone without distinction.

Conclusion

There has been a slow progress in the understanding of 'development' in the Church as well as outside. Initially the emphasis was more on economic development. Gradually the emphasis shifted to integral development or social development. Through social analysis we came to know that poverty in the world is purposely maintained by the vested interests of a few wealthy individuals or nations. Hence, development alone will not be able to address this issue of poverty and underdevelopment. There is a need to work towards liberation, which involves a fight against oppression, injustice and the unjust distribution of wealth.

There are various forces working against the integral development of individuals and nations. Faulty religious beliefs and practices, wastage of money in prestigious programmes, exaggerated defence expenses, structural adjustment policies, new economic policies, globalisation, invasion of multinational companies, voluntary retirement scheme, utter selfishness, large scale corruption, unequal treatment of women, high illiteracy rate, lack of health facilities for the poor, unemployment, underemployment, child labour, etc. are some of the factors which hinder the growth process. India as a nation is moving towards becoming a developed nation, but wealth is concentrated in the hands of the top ten percent of the people. As a result the gap between the rich and the poor is steadily increasing. The politicians, who are supposed to be living exemplary lives, are often leading scandalous lives and as a result they do not have any moral authority to lead the country to be a prosperous nation.

The Church in India has been successful to a great extent in its attempts at education and health care. After Vatican Council II, it is moving in the direction of identification with the poor, conscientizing the marginalized, integral development of the masses, etc. Since there are many landlords and politicians who are opposed to education and development, the Church personnel are facing strong opposition by way of persecution, false legal cases, intimidation, etc. The Church needs to involve itself in a more scientific manner. Though some have done studies in social work, more people need to be equipped with the tools of social analysis and organizing people.

Notes

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38. Cf. Paul Puthanangady, "Evangelii Nuntiandi: Reflections on some of its Salient Points," *Indian Missiological Review*, Jan. 1984) 85.
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44. SRS 40.